

LLM Cognitive Judgements Differ From Human

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Abstract

Large Language Models (LLMs) have lately been on the spotlight of researchers, businesses, and consumers alike. While the linguistic capabilities of such models have been studied extensively, there is growing interest in investigating them as *cognitive subjects*. In the present work I examine GPT-3 and ChatGPT capabilities on an limited-data inductive reasoning task from the cognitive science literature. The results suggest that these models' cognitive judgements are not human-like.

Keywords— Large Language Models, GPT-3, ChatGPT, Inductive Reasoning, Cognitive Judgements

1 Introduction

Large Language Models (LLMs), as typified by OpenAI ChatGPT [23] have lately had massive impact on public opinion: out of a maximum of 100, the terms “ChatGPT” and “AI” surged from 0 and 28 respectively on 20 Nov. 2022 to 73 and 99 respectively on 30 Apr. 2023¹ This optimism is also reflected in the Markets, as valuations of “AI”-exposed companies have been surging [1]. Researchers have expressed mixed opinions about the true abilities of such models, ranging from strong claims about Artificial General Intelligence [8](Microsoft is a co-owner of OpenAI) and the seemingly anthropomorphic attribution of consciousness on such models [20] (which humans partially agree [29]), to dismissal of any emergent notion of intelligence or human-like behavior [10, 13, 18].

Perhaps most eloquently presented in [3], it is not clear if LLMs *understand* language, or if they are just very proficient at manipulating language symbols, which we humans are vulnerable to implicitly interpreting as coherent. In fact, even before the current generation of LLMs there has been a focus on uncovering general linguistic competencies and capabilities [16, 28, 31, 27], as well as the *human-likeness* of Language Models [16, 12]. In the same spirit, there have been extensive investigations of ChatGPT performance in Natural Language Processing (NLP) tasks [2], discovering good overall performance but poor ability when it comes to reasoning and specifically inductive reasoning, as well as extensively accounting ChatGPT failures [5]. Additionally, ChatGPT responses seem to accurately mimic human language use [9]. Could these positive results support claims of intelligence or consciousness of LLMs?

¹Data source: Google Trends (<https://www.google.com/trends>).

I propose that the strength of the evidence should be proportional to the strength of the claims made, and as such any emergent behaviours that seem to transcend the mere linguistic realm when it comes to the capacity of LLMs should be considered from a perspective of *cognition*.

2 Previous Work

An early work on GPT-3 [6] examined the responses qualitatively in what is designated an “Author’s Turing Test” and found inconsistent behaviour: “*[GPT-3 is] not better than our very best writers and philosophers at their peak. Are its best moments better than many humans and even perhaps, our best writers at their worst? Quite possibly* [11]. Other works have focused on evaluating LLMs in experiments from the cognitive psychology literature and the *human-likeness* of their responses. [4] found GPT-3 to mostly give human-like responses. A recurring problem, however, with these studies is the explicit memorization of the materials. Asking GPT-3 about the tasks in [4], I found that many of the tasks employed (all of Kahneman & Tversky’s, Wason’s Card Selection task, and the Blicket task) could be accurately recited by the model.

An assortment of works study the Theory of Mind (ToM) of LLMs - the ability to attribute mental states to others. [17] examined both ChatGPT and GPT-4 ToM using material from Kahneman & Tversky. Similarly to [4], I found that ChatGPT could accurately recite all the tasks. The GPT-4 ToM was also qualitatively investigated in [14] using 10 philosophical paradoxes. Here too, I found that ChatGPT (the predecessor model) could recite 9 out of the 10 paradoxes. Another work focusing on ChatGPT ToM applied clinical methods used to assess pathological ToM in humans [7]. The model in general performed poorly and not similarly to humans in most tasks.

More closely related to the present work, [21] performed a neuropsychological investigation of abilities related to prefrontal functioning and found ChatGPT unable to mimic human cognitive functioning accurately. [19] studied GPT-3 as pragmatic reasoner and found human-like behaviour, albeit with some exceptions. Finally, [32] investigated ChatGPT and GPT-4 on a range of psychological tasks classified by the degree of embodiment associated with each and found that LLM responses deviated from human on sensory and motor judgements.

In this work, I focus on [15] from the cognitive science literature. The authors support the hypothesis that when faced with inductive problems with limited data available, human cognitive judgments closely correspond to those of a Bayesian model with fitting priors. The motivation for choosing this particular study is firstly there is no true answer to be determined deductively and as such it seems ideal to reveal the underlying cognitive workings of a mind, and secondly GPT-3 had no knowledge whatsoever about the work, while ChatGPT was able to give a somewhat accurate high-level overview but could not recite any particular experiment presented in the original work, thus avoiding the common pitfall of model memorization of human responses.

3 Methods

In [15] all tasks involve predicting an extent or duration of a phenomenon given an intermediate value at an unknown time: given a value t , predict the final, total value t_{total} . Responses from 350 participants were compared to a Bayesian predictor which computes a probability over t_{total} : $p(t_{\text{total}}|t) \propto p(t|t_{\text{total}})p(t_{\text{total}})$. The authors found that human judgments are close to the optimal predictions of the Bayesian predictor.

Specifically, the tasks and respective t are: cake baking times (minutes), life spans (years), movie grosses (million US\$), poem lengths (number of lines), U.S. representatives’ terms (years), and telephone box office waiting times (minutes). I omit the “Movie Runtimes” and “Pharaohs” tasks that had high variance in human responses. I inferred the values for the mean human predictions and confidence intervals, as well as the predictions of the Bayesian models from the plots in the original work. I refer to [15] for further details on the prompts and the Bayesian predictors’ choice of priors.

For each task and prompt value I asked GPT-3 [25] and ChatGPT [24] the equivalent question 20 times, starting a new conversation each time. I skipped the overall introduction as it appears in the study and finished each prompt with “The answer must be a single number, not a range, with no explanation.”. E.g.: “Imagine you hear about a movie that has taken in 10 million dollars at the box office, but don’t know how long it has been running. What would you predict for the total amount of box office intake for that movie? The answer must be a single number, not a range, with no explanation.”. I manually went through the results and extracted the response value when applicable, rejecting answers where a range or a nonsensical value was given (the number of rejected answers is presented in Table 2). The Model answers and relevant code for reproducing the results are made available online ²

	Bayesian Prediction	GPT-3	ChatGPT
Cakes	11.5	30.1	16.5
Life Spans	2.5	5.6	3.4
Movie Grosses	20.2	34.9	160.5
Poems	5.6	28.6	20.1
Representatives	16.0	32.0	29.5
Waiting Times	20.7	31.3	37.3

Table 1: Mean Average Percentage Error between the medians of the proposed models and the human judgements

4 Results

I present the Mean Average Percentage Error between each model and the human judgements in Table 1. The Bayesian predictors of [15] have consistently the lowest error compared to either GPT-3 or ChatGPT. These results suggest that LLMs do not align with human cognition when it comes to inductive cognitive judgments about everyday phenomena under limited available data.

²<https://github.com/sotlampr/llm-cognitive-judgements>

Figure 1: Medians and bootstrap 68% confidence interval ($n = 1000$)

Comparing GPT-3 to ChatGPT, the latter is closer to human participants for most tasks, with the striking exception of the “Movie Grosses”, where ChatGPT was the most hesitant to answer.

Graphs similar to [15] can be seen in Figure 1. GPT-3 and ChatGPT demonstrate inconsistent predictions in a few cases regardless of the task, as seen in the empirical confidence intervals for e.g. “Cakes” at $t = 70$, “Movie Grosses” at $t = 100$ and “Representatives” at $t = 7$.

I present the percentage of instances where no meaningful response was given in Table 2. GPT-3 was able to answer meaningfully and succinctly in all cases, while ChatGPT was hesitant when it comes to “Life Spans” and “Movie Grosses”. Common responses for both tasks were similar to “*The answer is not possible to determine...*”, “*There is not enough information given to accurately predict...*”, “*I’m sorry, but I cannot provide...*”, “*Since I am an AI language model, I cannot...*”. Additionally, on the “Life Spans” tasks, ChatGPT answered 6 times that it would not be ethical to make such predictions.

These patterns in refusing to answer also appear in previous works such

Task	GPT-3	ChatGPT
Cakes	0.0	0.0
Life Spans	0.0	45.0
Movie Grosses	0.0	71.3
Poems	0.0	0.0
Representatives	0.0	3.0
Waiting Times	0.0	0.0

Table 2: Percentage of samples with no satisfactory answer

as [5, 30, 20, 22], possibly revealing the effect of prompt tuning done with InstructGPT [26], penalizing hallucinatory, counterfactual, or otherwise undesirable responses

5 Conclusion

I demonstrated a clear failure of popular LLMs when it comes to making inductive judgements with limited available data on everyday scenarios. Despite having a huge number of parameters and being trained on a huge amount of data, these models cannot accurately model basic statistical principles that the human mind seems to entrust, and which could be more accurately modelled with many orders of magnitude less parameters.

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